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Language Contact Between the Vietic Group and the Chinese Language

Le Duc Luan PhD

Associate Professor, Nguyen The Thanh University, Ho Chi Minh City

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ABSTRACT: Language contact occurs in most languages around the world, and Vietnamese also comes into contact with many language groups. However, in this paper, we limit our study to linguistic contact between the Vietic language group and Chinese. Language contact occurs at many levels of language, but in this article, we only study language contact in the context of compound words with reduplication of meaning.

Compound words repeating meaning is a type of isomorphic compound word. The morphemes in compound words repeating meaning are independent morphemes, which are monosyllabic words. The two morphemes in this compound word repeat or correspond to the same meaning, so they are called compound words repeating meaning. In a compound word with reduplicated meanings, one morpheme explains the meaning of the other.

The main points developed in this paper: 1. The Vietnamese-Sino language contact group. 2. The group of language contact between Vietnamese (Kinh) and Muong.

The primary research method is a comparative study of vocabulary between the Vietic and Chinese languages. The reference materials for this linguistic comparison are the Vietnamese Dictionary, the Sino-Vietnamese Dictionary, and the Viet-Muong Dictionary.

The theoretical framework for this paper is based on research findings regarding word meanings, the concept of compound words, and language groups. We will continue to study the linguistic contact between Vietnamese and other language groups.

KEYWORDS: compound words; repeating meaning; contact language; morpheme; ethnic group

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. General introduction

Language contact occurs in most languages around the world, and Vietnamese also comes into contact with many language groups. However, in this paper, we limit our study to linguistic contact between the Vietic language group and Chinese. Language contact occurs at many levels of language, but in this article, we only study language contact in the context of compound words with reduplication of meaning.

Language contact is both imposed and voluntary. Imposing between Chinese and Vietnamese because the Chinese feudal dynasties that invaded Vietnam should impose their language on the language system to make it easier to govern. Nguyen Tai Can viewed Vietnamese-Chinese contact as a multi-layered historical process, in which the period of Chinese domination was coercive, while the period after independence was voluntary and conscious contact [15]. The origin and formation process of Sino-Vietnamese reading. Hanoi: Social Sciences Publishing House. (Reprint: Hanoi National University Publishing House (2000)). So, before the Han Dynasty and after Vietnam gained independence, language contact took place voluntarily.

“In the Vietnamese vocabulary system, loanwords from Chinese are used very widely. Especially in the fields of culture, education, religion, military, law, medicine, economics, and politics, they are used with even greater importance. In official documents, loanwords from Chinese account for about 60% of the commonly used Vietnamese vocabulary; however, in the aforementioned fields, the percentage can reach over 80%.” [14, p. 85]. As a result, there is a team of Confucian feudal intellectuals and up to 60 - 80% of Vietnamese vocabulary has originated from Chinese words which were read by Vietnamese sound, so called Sino-Vietnamese words.

However, Mark J. Alves commented: “There is both comparative linguistic data and written documentation showing that lexical borrowing in Vietnamese extends back more than two thousand years, though the initial period of language contact is less certain. 28% of the Vietnamese vocabulary in the sample, or about 415 words of the 1,477 words in the database, is either clearly or probably borrowed, with another 2% which are less likely to be loanwords. Of the loanwords in Vietnamese in the database, 90% are from Chinese (less than one-third from the Han dynasty era and more than two-thirds from the Tang Dynasty era onward)” [2].

Vietnam is a multi-ethnic country, with 54 ethnic groups, meaning that Vietnam is a multilingual country. That is why, in the process of language contact, there is variation, the repetition of linguistic elements and repetition of meanings formed from this contact mechanism [27].

Composite words with repetition meaning have the form of a repeating morpheme and are generally classified in categories as reduplicative words. However, the composite words with repetition meaning and reduplicative words are fundamentally different. The

reduplicative word is created by converting phonetic from the original syllable and the generated word has a different meaning from the original. Meanwhile, the composite words that have repeating meanings are two different words randomly compounded. Among reduplicative words can be derived from phonetic variations between dialects. Composite words with repetition meaning have the form of repeating part or all of a syllable that is also reduplicative of the initial consonant and the rhyme of the word but is not derived from the repetition mechanism. This type of composite words meaning completely repeats and repeats some meaning means. The reduplicative words use the morphemes and words composite method but the word's repetition meaning has the form of both repetition meaning and reduplicative words. Reduplicative words and repetition words are common in many languages around the world but composite words with repetition meaning have the form of repeating phonetic are still not popular. [13]

The purpose of this article is to clarify a type of compound word through linguistic contact. In a compound word with reduplicated meanings, one morpheme explains the meaning of the other.

1.2. Literature review

Vietnamese linguists have mentioned compound words repeating meanings, but have not studied language contact in this type of compound word. They only mentioned the linguistic origin in historical studies of Vietnamese. The following authors researched on compound words repeating meanings [17, p. 93-99] is called a compound word reduplicating meanings [12, p. 20-25] also gave an overview of the characteristics of this compound word.

Studying vocabulary of Sino origin, Sino-Vietnamese researchers such as [26], [19] have established 132 words that are identified as ancient Sino-Vietnamese words, 51 words identified as Sino-Vietnamization (the author called as Variant Sino-Vietnamese), and 13 words considered as Sino-Vietnamization, while others treated as ancient Sino-Vietnamese. The research of the aforementioned authors contributes to identifying the types of Sino-Vietnamese words. Ancient Sino-Vietnamese words are the first class of words to come into contact with Vietnamese, while Sino-Vietnamization words are variations of Chinese words within the Vietnamese syllabic structure. In some cases, they are classified as reduplicated words, for example: binh lính, where "lính" is a variation of "binh".

The author's research on Vietnamese–Muong etymological vocabulary draws on previous studies by [4, p. 125–139] as well as publications of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR (Muong Language and the Russian Academy of Sciences (Ruc Language [23].

Researches on ancient Vietnamese language were made by [26]. The author documented the medieval Vietnamese language containing elements of ancient Vietnamese [1], [21]; [3]; [25, p.327-343].

Vu Duc Nghieu [25, p. 98] referred to the Proto-Vietnamese-Muong speaking inhabitants. From the Viet-Muong language, it was split into two branches: the Proto Viet and the Proto Muong from around the 18th-19th centuries. Pre-ancient Vietnamese was formed in the 10th – 12th centuries and ancient Vietnamese was from the 13th – 16th centuries. This was also the stage of forming the current North Central (Nghe An, Ha Tinh) dialects [25, p. 230-231], [16] in the Vietnamese phonetic history textbook. He based on phonetic data, said that the former Viet-Muong residents were divided into two masses: a mass stayed in the Northwest mountainous region and the other went down to the Northern Delta. The mass going down the plains was heavily influenced by the Tay - Tai language speaking inhabitants. Studying dialects in Vietnamese: [11] Muong language in the Central dialect [5]. Vietnamese Dialect Dictionary [7] in the Vietnamese dialects.

Research on language contact between Chinese and Austronesian languages L. Gagart 1993: 1-63 made a list of 222 lexical comparisons with the ancestry relationship between these two languages and in 1994. In the work "Proto- Austronesian and old Chinese evidence for Sino- Austronesian, he gave 56 lexical correspondences and phonetic correspondences in words belonging to the basic lexical class with Sino- Austronesian relationships. According to [6, p. 19] mentioned that the position of Vietnamese must be in the Austroasiatic family, between the Palung-Wa group in the Northwest and the Mon Khme group in the Southwest.

2. THORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1. Thoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this paper is based on research findings regarding word meanings, the concept of compound words, and language groups

2.2. Research methodology

The primary research method is a comparative study of vocabulary between the Vietic and Chinese languages. The reference materials for this linguistic comparison are the Vietnamese Dictionary, the Sino-Vietnamese Dictionary, and the Viet-Muong Dictionary.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Vietnamese - Sino language contact group

3.1.1. Repeating an ancient Sino-Vietnamese and Sino-Vietnamese element

Previously, this layer was called 古漢越字 'Old Sino-Vietnamese' by [24], recently, however [20], in an extensive study of Sino-Vietnamese, chose the term 'Early Sino-Vietnamese' to avoid confusion with the use of 'old' for reconstructions of proto-languages. The elements "buồn, dòi, cô, cã, mù, nghề, muôn, ngờ" in these combinations are old Sino-Vietnamese words. This is the transformation movement of the Vietnamese phonetic mechanism that caused Sino-Vietnamese words to change into Vietnamese sounds completely and they lose their mark in the Sino-Vietnamese character system. They work freely in Vietnamese communication.

Buồn phiền (sad) (adj): "phiền" 烦: buồn lo, sầu khổ: "phiền muôn" 煩悶 buồn rầu.

Di dời (relocate) (v): "di" 移 (shift): chuyển, dòi: 轉移陣地 di chuyển trận địa (transfer position).

Đơn cô (lonely) (adj): "đơn" 单(single): đơn chiếc, một, đơn độc, cô cút: 形單影隻 Hình đơn bóng lẻ (single, alone)

Giá cả (prices) (n): "giá" 價(price): giá tiền, giá cả, giá trị (value): 物價 giá hàng (price); 無價之寶 của quý vô giá (priceless).

Mùi vị (taste) (n): “vị” 味(taste): mùi: hương vị 香味 mùi thơm (fragrance).

Muôn vạn (ten thousand) (n): “muôn”: a type of “vạn” 萬 (million), “vàn” is variant from “vạn”: muôn, mười ngàn: 萬紫千紅 Muôn hồng nghìn tía (Colorful).

Nghề nghiệp (occupation): “nghiệp” 業 : nghề: 工農業 công nông nghiệp (Industry and Agriculture).

“Nghi ngờ (doubt) (v): “nghi” 疑 (suspect): ngờ, không tin, ngờ vực, nghi hoặc (doubt, distrust): 可疑 khả nghi, đáng ngờ (suspicious).

Most of the old Sino-Vietnamese variations have been used for a long time and become popular in Vietnamese communication, but there are also a few words that are rarely used, losing the meaning such as “cả” in “giá cả (price)”. This type of repetition may be that a word introduced later is supplemented by a word introduced earlier into Vietnam to explain its meaning.

The elements: “buồn” in “buồn phiền” (sadness/frustration), “dời” in “đi dời” (relocation), “đơn” in “đơn côi” (lonely/solitary), “cả” in “giá cả” (price), “mùi” in “mùi vị” (smell/flavor), “muôn” in “muôn vạn” (ten thousand/million), “nghề” in “nghề nghiệp” (occupation/profession), and “ngờ” in “nghi ngờ” (doubt/suspicion) are ancient Sino-Vietnamese elements. These are variant syllables from ancient Chinese that came into contact with the Vietnamese language during the prehistoric period. [12]

3.1.2. Repeating a Sino-Vietnamese and Sino-Vietnamization element

A variant Sino-Vietnamese is called Sino-Vietnameseization by some linguists as [25, p. 163-171]. It is actually a phenomenon of phonetic variation, phonetic transformation from one Sino-Vietnamese sound to another according to the rules of phonetic transformation but it still retains Sino-Vietnamese sounds without losing its accent like ancient Sino-Vietnamese words. Wang’s [24, p. 76–77 and p. 380–381] in the groundbreaking articles on Sino-Vietnamese historical linguistics, he offered no phonological explanation but categorized these as nativized forms following Vietnamese pronunciation, what he termed 越化 yuè huà ‘Vietnamized’, which suggests that these were loanwords modified later after borrowing from Chinese. The variant Sino-Vietnamese which is called Sino-Vietnamization by some linguists, is actually the phenomenon of phonetic variation, phonetic transformation from a Sino-Vietnamese sound to another according to the law of phonetic transformation, but still retains the Sino-Vietnamese sound without traceless like ancient Sino-Vietnamese. This type is divided into the following two groups:

a. In compound words repeating meaning, there is the phenomenon of a Sino-Vietnamese phonetic inflected and then paired with the previous phonetic. This group contains the words “câu, gửi, in, lẽ”:

Cầu kiều (bridge) (n): “kiều” 橋: “cầu” (bridge): 架橋 “bác cầu” (bridge).

Kí gửi (send, deposit) (v): “kí” 寄: “gửi, gởi”: chuyển đi (send): 寄信 gửi thư (send a letter).

In ấn (print) (v): “in” (print), “ấn” 印(seal): “ấn thư” 印書 in sách (print book).

Lí lẽ (argument) (n): “lí” 理 (reason) “lẽ” (grounds): lí lẽ: 合理 hợp lí (reasonable).

b. The second group, a variant Sino-Vietnamese element paired with the native Sino-Vietnamese element. This group contains the words: “cớ, đáng, khiến, phước, thật, thừa, vạ”:

Cầu khiến (request): “cầu” 求 (implore): xin giúp, nhờ: “khẩn cầu” 懇求 (plead). “khiến” (induce): muốn ai đó làm gì (want someone to do something).

Chân thật (trueful) (adj): “chân” 真: “thật” turning into “thực”, chân thực (true, honest): chân đế 眞諦 đạo lí chân thực (true morality).

Chứng cứ (evidence) (n): “chứng” 證: “cứ” 據: bằng chứng (proof), chứng cứ (evidence): 無憑無據 không có chứng cứ gì cả (there's no proof). “Cứ” turning into “cớ”.

Hình dạng (shape) (n): “hình” 形 (form): dáng, vẻ: hình thái 形態 dáng vẻ bên ngoài (appearance). “Dạng” 樣 (kind): kiểu, hình dáng (style, shape). “Dạng” turning into “dáng”, “dòng”: hình dáng, hình dòng (shape, figure).

Phúc lộc (happiness and wealth) (n): “phúc” 福 (happy, blessing): hưởng phúc 享福 (enjoy the blessing), “lộc” 祿: phúc, tốt lành: phúc lộc 福祿. “Phúc” is variant from “phước”.

Tai họa (catastrophe, misfortune) (adj): “tai” 災: nạn, họa hại (accident): “thủy tai” 水災 (flood). “Họa” (disaster): 禍 turning into “vạ”.

In this category, most of the variant Sino-Vietnamese elements are not commonly used in communication languages such as ancient Sino-Vietnamese words. [12]

3.1.3. Repeating ancient Sino-Vietnamese elements with native Vietnamese elements

The ancient Sino-Vietnamese elements have shown as Vietnamese sound and had no sign of Chinese phonetic symbols, so when combined with Vietnamese words, it was thought to be combined by two Vietnamese elements. In this category we find ancient Sino-Vietnamese words: âu, bằng, bì, bóc, bùa, bụa, buộc, buồn, buồn, buồn, bùng, can, che, chia, chím, chùa, chứa, cỏi, dẫu, đảm, họ, kén, là, lừa, lười, mã, mù, phẳng, tìm, tuổi... This category has the following typical words:

Âu lo (worry, anxious) (v): “lo” (worry), “âu” is ancient sound of “ưu” (sad) 忧: buồn rầu, lo âu, ưu phiền (worry, careworn): 烦.

Bằng phẳng (flat) (adj): “bằng” is ancient sound of “bình” 坪: bằng phẳng (flat): “địa bình” 地平 đất bằng (flat ground), “bình đẳng” 平等 ngang hàng (equality).

Bó buộc (bind) (v): “bó” (bundle), “buộc” (tie) means using a rope to bundle an object.

Bóc lột (exploit) (v): “bóc” (remove) has the same meaning with “lột” (peel).

Bùa ngải (charm) (v): “bùa” has the same meaning with “ngải”.

Buôn bán (sell) (v): “buôn” has the same meaning with “bán”.

Buồn rầu (sad) (adj): “buồn” has the same meaning with “rầu, sầu 愁, phiền”.

Buông thả (dissolute) (v): “buông” has the same meaning with “thả”.

Bưng bê (hold) (v): “bưng” has the same meaning with “bê”.

Can ngăn (prevent) (v): “can” has the same meaning with “ngăn”, can gián (dissuade) 諫 (admonish).

Che đậy (cover) (v): “che” has the same meaning with “đậy”, che phủ.

Chia lia (separate) (v): “chia” has the same meaning with “lia”, chia li, “lia” may be the phonetic variation of “li” 離.

Chìm đắm (sink) (v): “chìm” has the same meaning with “đắm”, chìm thuyền, đắm thuyền (boat sink, boat wreck). “Chìm” may be phonetic variation of “trầm” 沈.

Chứa đựng (contain) (v): “chứa” has the same meaning with “đựng”.

Dầu mỡ (grease and oil) (n): “dầu” has the same meaning with “mỡ”.

Đầm đìa (fullness) (n): “đầm (swamp)” has the same meaning with “đìa, ao pond)” (it itself is a noun but when combined, it turns the meaning into an adjective).

Giống họ (family) (n): “họ” has the same meaning with “giống”.

Góa bụa (widow) (adj): “bụa” has the same meaning with “góa”, góa chồng.

Kén chọn (select) (v): “kén” has the same meaning with “chọn”.

Mồ mã (grave) (n): “mả” has the same meaning with “mồ”, “mồ” may be the phonetic variation of “mộ” 墓 (tomb).

Mù lòa (blind) (adj): “mù” has the same meaning with “lòa”.

Lụa là (silk) (n): “là” has the same meaning with “lụa”.

Lừa gạt (deceive) (v): “lừa” has the same meaning with “gạt”.

Lười nhác (lazy) (adj): “lười” has the same meaning with “nhác”.

Tìm kiếm (seek) (v): “tìm” has the same meaning with “kiếm”.

Among the words of this group, there are words such as “bó buộc”, “buôn bán”, “bưng bê”, “chia lia”, “đầm đìa”, “mồ mã”, “lụa là”. There is a fake form of reduplicative words, which some Vietnamese linguists mistakenly consider them to be reduplicative words. Among them, there is phonetic variation like “mồ mã”, “chia lia”, “lụa là”. [12]

3.1.4. Repeating the Sino-Vietnamese elements with the native ancient Vietnamese elements

Most of the ancient Vietnamese elements are not commonly communicated, so their meanings are obscured, while most Sino-Vietnamese elements are used frequently, so they operate freely in speech like Vietnamese. Therefore, in this category, Sino-Vietnamese elements explain the meaning of ancient Vietnamese one. Most Vietnamese people do not understand the meaning of words “táp”, “tật”, “chiến”, “rối”, “do”, “áng”, “hóc”, “lộ”, “khứ”, “rẻ”, “bại”, “muông”, “tác” that must be interpreted from accompanying Sino-Vietnamese elements.

Bao bọc (wrap) (v): “bao” 包 (package): bọc (wrap), gói (package) “bao thư” 包書 gói sách (packaging book).

Báo đền (recompense) (v): “báo” 報: báo ân (repaying kindness), báo đáp (requite) 答.

Bệnh tật (sickness) (n): “bệnh”: 病 ốm, đau (sick): “tâm bệnh” (emotional illness) 心病, “tật” 疾: bệnh (disease). Illness will lead to disability.

Cấm đoán (forbidden) (v): “đoán”: cấm 禁 (ban).

Cuối cùng (final) (adj): “cùng” 窮: cuối, tận, hết (end, final, last); “cuối” may be variant from “cùng”.

Cúng quai (worship) (v): “quai”: cúng 供.

Do thám (spy) (v): thám 探 (explore): dò, tìm: 探源 (Explore the source) dò tìm nguồn gốc; 探問 (Inquire) dò hỏi; dò xét: 密探 mật thám (beagle). “Do” is variant from “dò”, Synonymous combinations “dò tìm”, “dò xét”.

Dối trá (lie) (adj): “trá” 詐 (deceive): dối, giả dối, lừa dối.

Đề bài (question) (n): “đề” 題: bài thi (exam): “thí đề” 試題 đề bài thi (test question).

Đồng áng (field) (n): “đồng” 垌 ruộng đất (field), “ang”: đồng bằng (plain) (Lê: Hai Nam), “ang” is variant into “áng”: mảnh đất ruộng chưa cấy (piece of land has not been transplanted rice).

Hẹn ước (promise) (v): “hẹn” (make a tryst), “ước” 約: hẹn is also “ước hẹn”.

Hiểm hóc (danger) (adj): “hiểm” 險: nguy hiểm, hiểm hóc, hiểm độc (dangerous): 險.

Khách khứa (guest) (n): khách 客 (customer): môn khách, khách khứa: 會客. “Khứa” also means “guest”.

Khinh rẻ (misprize) (v): khinh (contempt) 輕: Khinh rẻ, khinh bi, coi thường (Disdain, contempt, despise): “khinh địch” 輕敵 (hostile).

Lo âu (worry) (v): “âu”: is old sound of “ưu” 忧: lo (worry).

Lụn bại (decline) (adj): “bại” (defeat) 敗: tàn, rụng: “lụn”: tàn lụi (wither).

Muông thú (animal) (n): “thú” 兽: thú vật, súc vật: 野獸 thú rừng (wild animals live in the forest); “muông”: thú vật (animal).

Nảy phó (entrust) (v): “nảy”: giao (deliver), giao phó (entrust, assign) 付 like “nảy trao”.

Nuôi dưỡng (foster) (v): “dưỡng” 养: nuôi (foster), nuôi nấng, nuôi dưỡng (raise, nurture, rear).

Riêng tây (adj): “tây” (personal): riêng, tây is old sound of “tư” 私: riêng tư (private).

Sai quấy (wrong) (adj): “quấy”: sai (false) 差 sai lầm (mistake), sai trái (wrong).

Sức lực (force) (n): “lực” 力: sức (strength), 人力 sức người, nhân lực (human power, manpower).

Tang chế (mourning) (n): “tang” (funeral) 喪: lễ tang (funeral), cư tang 居喪 (bereavement) để tang, “chế” also means “tang”.

Trợ giúp (help) (v): “trợ” 助 (help): giúp đỡ.

Tuổi tác (age) (n): “tuổi” also means “tác”.

Từ giã (farewell) (v) “từ”: 辭 từ biệt (separation), từ giã.

Xâm lấn (invade) (v): “xâm” 侵: lấn chiếm, mạo phạm (encroach, offense): “xâm chiếm” 侵占 (invasion) lấn lầy. [12]

3.1.5. Repeating a Sino- Vietnamese element and a native Vietnamese element

Variant Sino-Vietnamese words work as freely in speech as words like Vietnamese, when combined in Vietnamese compound words, they have independent meanings. The variant Sino-Vietnamese words in compound words repeating meaning are “chào, châu, đai, gắng, ghi, khuyên, lãi, mù, thay”. The following are typical words:

Chào hỏi (greet) (v): “chào (greet)” is also “hỏi (ask)”, for Vietnamese, to ask is to greet.

Châu chực (waiting) (v): “chực” is also “châu”, “chờ” (wait). Waiting to hear the verdict and receive the assignment.

Cố gắng (endeavour) (v): “cố” (try) is also “gắng” (strive to).

Ghi chép (record) (v): “ghi” has the same meaning with “chép” (write).

Đất đai (land) (n): “đất” is also đai, may be the phonetic variation of “địa”.

Đui mù (blind) (adj): “đui” is also “mù”.

Khuyên răn (advice) (v): “khuyên” is also “răn”.

Lời lãi (interest) (n): “lời” is also lãi.

Thay thế (replace) (v): “thế” is also thay.

For some words such as “châu chực”, “đất đai”, “lời lãi”, due to the lack of thorough study, some Vietnamese linguists called it the reduplicative words, in fact they just have the same phenomenon. [12]

4. GROUP OF LANGUAGE CONTACT OF VIETNAMESE (KINH) – MUONG

4.1. Modern Vietnamese and Ancient Vietnamese

This type examines and statistics two morphemes, in which, one morpheme is the modern Vietnamese language and the other is the old Vietnamese morpheme. Modern Vietnamese elements can be followed to explain the meaning of ancient Vietnamese that have lost their meaning. If standing alone, many elements of ancient Vietnamese have no meaning and are ambiguous. In ancient Vietnamese words, it is possible that there are linguistic elements of ethnic groups that are Vietnamization (Kinh).

Âm thầm (silent) (adj): “âm”: thầm lặng (silently).

Bồng ẵm (carry) (v): “ẵm”: bồng, bế (hold in the arms) like “bồng bế”.

Bếp núc (kitchen) (n): “núc”: bếp, hòn núc.

Bởi vì (because) (conj): “bởi”: vì, do (due to, because), like “bởi chưng”.

Cả lớn (big) (adj): “cả”: lớn, to (big, large).

Cả thảy (whole) (đ): “cả”: thảy, tất thảy, tất cả (all, whole, entire) like “tất thảy”.

Chê bai (disparage) (v): “bai”: chê.

Chênh lệch (uneven, unequal) (adj): “chênh” (tilted): lệch (skewed), thiên lệch (skewed, biased) like “chéch lệch”: “chéch”: xiên, lệch (slanted, skewed).

Chùa chiền (pagoda) (n): “chùa” also means “chiền”, also referred to as: chùa thiên, già chiền.

Chút ít (little) (n): “chút”: ít, lượng ít ỏi (a small number) like “chút đỉnh”: “đỉnh”: chút, lượng nhỏ (a little bit).

Chừng mức (level) (n): “chừng”: mức độ (degree) like “chừng mực”.

Cong vạy (bent) (adj): “vạy”: cong, không ngay thẳng (curved, not straight), tà vạy, vạy vọ.

Cúng đơm (worshiped) (v): “đơm” (serve out rice into bowls): cúng, also referred to as “đơm quai, cúng quai”.

Cưu mang (adopt) (v): “cưu”: mang, giữ, mang thai, đùm bọc, che chở (carry, hold, take care of, protect).

Đôi theo (follow) (v): “đôi”: theo, tuân theo, noi theo (follow, obey, abide by).

Dọn dẹp (clean) (v): “dọn”: dẹp, sắp xếp (clean up, arrange).

Đuồng bỏ (abandon) (v): “đuồng”: bỏ (abandon), bỏ bê (neglect), xua đuổi (banish), “ruồng bỏ” is also referred to as “đuồng dẫy”.

Dường như (seem) (k): dường: như, hình như, có vẻ như (like, seem, look), also referred to as “dường bằng”.

Đầy dẫy (full) (adj): “dẫy” (overflow): đầy tràn (overflowing), also referred to as “đầy rẫy”.

Đê bỏ (abandon) (v): “đê”: bỏ, li dị (divorce).

Đoái lại (look back) (v): “đoái”: ngoảnh lại, nghĩ tới (look back, think about).

Đòi theo (claim) (v): “đòi”: theo (conform), tùy theo (depending).

Đón ngửa (pick up) (v): “ngửa”: đón (receive), đón rước.

Đồng nội (filed) (n): “nội”: cánh đồng (plain).

Đống đẫy (pile) (adj): “đống”: đầy, nhiều, also referred to as “đầy đống”.

Đùa cợt (joke) (v): “cợt”: đùa giỡn, trêu ghẹo (joke, tease) like “bỡn cợt, đùa bỡn”.

Đụn lẫm (barn) (n): “lẫm”: kho chứa thóc (rice storage), “đụn”: kho thóc (barn).

Đường sá (street) (n): “sá”: đường (road).

E ngại (fear) (v): “e”: ngại, sợ (fear, be shy of) like “e lệ”.

Ghê biệt (separation) (v): “ghê”: chia ly, biệt ly, chia rẽ (farewell).

Giữ gìn (keep): “gìn”: giữ (hold), also referred to as “gìn giữ”.

- Hay biết (know) (v): “hay”: biết, hiểu rõ (know, understand).
- Héo don (wither) (adj): “don” (thin): héo, khô, quắt lại (wilted, dry, shriveled).
- Hiểm hóc (rugged and inaccessible) (adj): “hóc” (narrowest spot) can be dangerous: hiểm, hiểm trở (rugged).
- Họa may (perchance) (p): “họa”: may ra, may chăng (luckily) like “họa chăng”: ít khi, hiếm (rarely).
- Hối thúc (urge) (v): “hối”: thúc, giục, thúc giục.
- Hơn nữa (more) (adj): “nữa”: hơn.
- Im ắng (silent) (adj): “ắng”: im bật, vắng lặng
- Inh ỏi (noisy) (adj): “ôi”: inh: the sound is loud and jarring, ỏi: vang rân, om sòm.
- Kham chịu (endure) (v): “kham”: chịu được (withstand), also “cam chịu”.
- Kiêng khem (abstain) (v): “khem”: kiêng.
- Khen ngợi (compliment) (v): “ngợi”: khen, like “ca ngợi”, also “khen ngợi” (praise).
- Khinh dể (scorn) (v): “dể”: khinh, khinh rẻ (feel contempt for) like “dể duôi”.
- Giải bày (explain) (v): “giãi”: bày tỏ lòng mình cho người khác biết (express yourself to others).
- Giúp rập (assist) (v): “rập”: giúp (help).
- La đà (very low) (adj): “la”: đà: rất thấp, sà xuống thấp (swooping) like “là đà” (near to the surface).
- Lo toan (worry) (v): “toan”: lo liệu (make arrangements), toan tính (take care, calculate).
- Lỗi lầm (mistake) (v): “lỗi”: lầm, nhầm (mistake), sai (wrong).
- Lu mờ (dim) (adj): “lu”: mờ, không tỏ, lu li.
- Lừng lẫy (famous) (v): “lấy”: lừng, vang lừng (resound).
- Lười biếng (lazy): “biếng”: lười nhác (idle) like “giãi đãi”.
- Mãi mê (engross) (v): “mãi”: mê (favorite), tập trung cao vào việc gì đó (highly focus on something).
- Mắng diếc (scold) (v): “diếc”: mắng, also “mắng nhiếc” like “mắng mỏ, diếc dóc”.
- Mầm mống (germ) (n): “mống”: mầm mới nảy (newly sprouted, seed).
- Meo mồm (moldy) (adj hoặc n): “mồm”: meo.
- Năn nỉ (beg) (v): năn nỉ: nài nỉ (supplicant), xin khẩn khoản (plead). “
- Ngay thẳng (straight) (adj): “ngay”: thẳng, ngay thật (straight, honest).
- Ngặt nghèo” (difficult) (adj): “ngặt”: nghèo.
- Nghèo hèn (poverty) (adj): “hèn”: nghèo (poor) like “hèn kém”.
- Nghỉ ngơi (rest) (v): “ngơi”: nghỉ, ngừng, ngủ (rest, stop, sleep).
- Nhỏ mọn (flimsy) (adj): “mọn”: nhỏ “nhỏ bé”.
- Nhờ cậy (ask for help) (v): “cậy”: nhờ (ask), also “cậy nhờ”.
- Noi theo (follow) (v): “noi”: theo, làm theo (abide by, follow).
- Nóng sốt (hot) (adj): “sốt” (fever): nóng, nóng nực, bức sốt.
- Nối tiếp (connect) (v): “nối”: tiếp (next), liền theo sau (next, immediately following).
- Ôm ấp (hug) (v): “ấp”: ôm.
- Quạnh vắng (desolate) (adj): “quạnh”: vắng (solitary) và yên lặng (quiet), quạnh hiu (desolate, desert).
- Sắm sửa (prepare) (v): “sắm”: sửa soạn, chuẩn bị (make ready), tính liệu (prepare).
- Siêng năng (diligent) (adj): “năng”: siêng, siêng sức, cần mẫn (laborious).
- So le (unequal) (adj): “le”: so, không đều, không bằng nhau (uneven, unequal).
- So bì (compare) (v): “bì”: so, sánh.
- Sự việc (event) (n): “sự”: việc, chuyện (event, fact).
- Sương móc (dew) (n): móc: sương (fog).
- Rẻ khinh (misprize) (v): “rẻ”: khinh, also “khinh rẻ” (contempt).
- Rêu rao (divulge) (v): “rêu”: rao (to advertise).
- Rõ rệt (clearly) (adj): “rệt”: rõ; “tỏ rõ” (express), “tỏ”: rõ ràng (clear)
- Roi vọt (cane) (n): “vọt” (give one whip): roi (whip, cane, rod).
- Rùng rợn (macabre) (adj): “rùng”: ghê rợn (horrifying).
- Tách rời (split) (v): “tách”: rời, bỏ đi, rời khỏi (leave).
- Tập dượt (practice) (v): “dượt”: tập, tập lại, làm lại cho thành thạo (practice, rehearse, repeat to mastery).
- Thẳng băng (straightforward) (adj): “băng”: thẳng.
- Thết đãi (treat) (v): “đãi”: thết, also “đãi đãi, đãi đưa” (entertain, banquet, feast)
- Thôi rồi (it's done) (v): “thôi”: xong, rồi, khỏi (complete, end).
- Thuộc lâu (remember word by word) (adj): “lâu”: rất thuộc, thông thạo (very familiar, well versed) also “thuộc lâu, lâu thông”.
- Thưa gửi (ask) (v): gửi: thưa, also: “gửi thưa”, “thưa thốt” (speak): “thốt”: thưa, nói.
- Thương xót (pity, feel compassion for) (v): “xót”: thương cảm (compassion).
- Thơm ngát (fragrant) (adj): “ngát”: thơm, mùi thơm dễ chịu (fragrant, pleasant scent).
- Tị nạnh (envy) (v): “tị”: nạnh, so sánh thiệt hơn với người khác (compare with others).
- Tiêu pha (spend) (v): “pha”: tiêu dùng (consumption).
- Tốt đẹp (good) (adj): “tốt”: đẹp (pretty).

- Tuổi tác (age) (n): “tác”: tuổi (age).
Tương tựa (similar) (v): “tựa”: tương tựa như (likewise) also “tương tự”: giống như thế (like that).
Trang lứa (peer) (n): “trang”: lứa, cùng một tuổi, cùng lứa (same age).
Trắng phau (pretty white) (adj): “phau”: rất trắng (very white).
Tre pheo (n): “pheo”: tre (bamboo) (Muong language: peo).
Trọn vẹn (complete) (adj): “vẹn”: trọn, vẹn vè: đầy đủ; vẹn vang: trọn vẹn hoàn toàn (full, complete).
Ủ rũ (glumpy) (adj): “ủ”: rũ, héo rũ, rầu rĩ (droopy, wilting sullen).
Ướt át (wet) (adj): “át”: ướt.
Vây bọc (encirclement) (v): “bọc” (cover): vây (surround, encircle).
Vi lễ” (have regard for) (v): “vi”: lễ trọng, yêu vi (respect).
Vốn liếng (capital) (n): “liếng”: vốn.
Xông pha (brave) (v): “pha”: xông vào (get in).
Yêu dấu (my dearly) (v): “dấu”: yêu (love), (May, Ma Lieng language: azu, aju; Sách: Zu, ju: thương), also “dấu yêu”. [12]

4.2. Vietnamese (Kinh) – Muong language

According [11] in the Muong language in Central dialect, this type examines and statistics two morphemes, in which, one is Vietnamese and one is Muong:

- Bầu bạn (friend) (n): in Muong language, “bầu” is also “bạn”.
Bông hoa (flower) (n): “bông”: hoa, “pong” (Mường, Rục, Thà Vưng languages).
Bờ cõi (border) (n): in Muong language, “cõi” means “bờ”, tree fence.
Chửi bới (scold, yell) (v): in Muong language, “bới” also means “chửi”.
Giận dữ (angry) (v): In Muong language, “dữ” means “giận”.
Hỏi han (ask) (v): “han”: hỏi (Thà Vưng language: haan, Muong language: han).
Ít ỏi (scanty) (adj): In Muong language, “ỏi” means “ít” (few).
Khách khứa (guest) (n): In Muong language: khách khứa: “khứa” is also “khách”.
Mơ nang (spathe) (n): “nang”: mơ, mơ cau (In Muong language: nang, cau. “Mơ cau” is a material used to wrap rice).
Mua chác (buy) (v): “mua” in Muong language, “chác” means “mua”.
Nhão bết (pasty) (adj): “nhão” in Muong language, “bết” means “nhão”.
Sân sướng (yard) (n): In Muong language, “sướng” means “sân đất” under the house or in front of the house.
Xanh lè (green) (adj): In Muong language, “lè” also means “xanh”. [12]

Old Vietnamese originated from South Asian language groups, primarily the Viet language group, especially the Viet-Muong group. Therefore, morphemes from these sources are combined with morphemes in modern Vietnamese to form compound words with reduplicated meanings.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The compound words repeating meaning are a word that has independent morphemes put together to form a new word. These morphemes are themselves two independent syllables, standing alone as monosyllable. The meaning reduplication or repetition originates from the linguistic contact between Vietnamese and Chinese language, between sounds of the same language origin and even in native Vietnamese but between dialects and common languages, between modern Vietnamese and old Vietnamese.

Language contact in this compound word can be divided into the following contact groups: Sino-Vietnamese contact group, Vietnamese - Muong language contact group, Vietnamese-Tay Tai language contact group, Vietnamese-Khme language contact group, Vietnamese - Polynesian language contact group, Vietnamese -Indo-European contact group. In particular, the Sino-Vietnamese contact group and the Vietnamese-Muong language contact group were more numerous than the other groups. Group of Vietnamese - the Truong Son ethnic groups, Central Highland and group of Vietnamese Kinh with Indo-European languages contact has the least number of compound words.

Initially, the compound words repeating meaning may be due to the need to explain the meaning between the inhabitants of different languages in order to understand each other's language. During use, they create new meanings compared to the meanings of compound morphemes. This study aims to contribute to the study of the process of language contact and the meaning factors in compound words repeating meaning. Due to the volume of articles in the journal, the analytical data shows only typical compound words repeating meaning.

Most morphemes in reduplicative compound words are independent morphemes derived from different linguistic sources. However, in many cases, the second morpheme is a phonological variant of the first. In addition to reduplicative compounds consisting of synonymous morphemes, there are also forms in which the morphemes are not synonymous. Vietnamese reduplicative compounds often contain two synonymous morphemes, whereas in English the same meaning is typically expressed by a single word.

REFERENCES

- 1) A de Rhodes (1991), Từ điển Annam-Lusitan-Latinh (Dictionarivm Annamiticvm Lvsitanvm, et Latinvm ope), Nxb Khoa học Xã hội, Hà Nội.
- 2) Alves, Mark J (2018), Chinese Loanwords in Vietnamese Pronouns and Terms of Address and Reference, in Proceedings of the 29th North American Conference on Chinese Linguistics (NACCL-29), 2017, Volume 1, ed. by Marjorie K.M. Chan and Hana Kang, 286-303. Columbus, Ohio: The Ohio State University. https://www.academia.edu/33556335/Chinese_Influence_on_Vietnamese_Pronouns_and_terms_of_address_and_reference_toaR.

- 3) Aj.L. Taberd (2004), Dictionarium Anamitico Latinnum, Center for National Cultural Studies, Nxb. Văn học, Trung tâm nghiên cứu Quốc học.
- 4) Diffloth G (1991), Vietnamese as a Mon-Khme language, Paper from the first annual meeting of the Southeast Asian linguistics society.
- 5) Đặng Thanh Hòa (2005), Từ điển phương ngữ tiếng Việt [Vietnamese dialect dictionary] Nxb. Đà Nẵng-Trung tâm từ điển học.
- 6) Haudricout A. G. (1991), Vị trí của tiếng Việt trong các ngôn ngữ Nam Á [Location of Vietnamese in the South Asian language] Hà Nội: Ngôn ngữ, số 1.
- 7) Hoàng Thị Châu (2009), Phương ngữ học tiếng Việt [Vietnamese dialects] Hà Nội: Nxb. Đại học Quốc gia.
- 8) Hoàng Phê (editor-in-chief) (2016), Từ điển tiếng Việt [Vietnamese Dictionary] Thanh Hóa: Nxb Hồng Đức.
- 9) Huỳnh, Tịnh Paulus Của (2018), Đại Nam Quốc âm tự vị, Cuốn 1 và 2 [Đại Nam Quốc âm words, Book 1 and 2] Nxb. Tổng hợp thành phố Hồ Chí Minh.
- 10) Lê Đình Khấn (2002), Từ vựng gốc Hán trong Tiếng Việt [Words of Chinese Origin in Vietnamese] Nhà xuất bản Đại học Quốc Gia Hồ Chí Minh.
- 11) Lê Đức Luận (2015), Tiếng Mường trong phương ngữ miền Trung [Muong language in the Central dialect] Hà Nội: Ngôn ngữ, số 11.
- 12) Lê Đức Luận (2019), Các yếu tố cấu tạo trong từ ghép lấy nghĩa [Mechanism of meaning combination in compound words with repetition of meaning] Hà Nội: Tạp chí Ngôn ngữ và Đời sống, pp. 20-25.
- 13) Lê Đức Luận, Hồ Văn Hận (2025), Morpheme Repetition where two Syllables Repeat the Meaning International, Journal of Human Research and Social Science Studies ISSN(p): 3050-547X, ISSN(e): 3050-5488 Volume 02 Issue 11 November, 2025 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.55677/ijhrss/17-2025-Vol 02I11>
- 14) Lê Quang Thành (2022), Đọc thơ Đường – Bàn về từ mượn tiếng Hán trong tiếng Việt, Dạy và Học ngày nay, 4/2022, p. 85
- 15) Nguyễn Tài Cẩn (1979), Nguồn gốc và quá trình hình thành cách đọc tiếng Hán Việt [The Origins and Process of Development of Sino-Vietnamese Readings]. Hà Nội: Nhà xuất bản Khoa học Xã hội.
- 16) Nguyễn Tài Cẩn (1995), Giáo trình Lịch sử ngữ âm tiếng Việt [A Text on Vietnamese Historical Phonology]. Hà Nội: Nhà xuất bản Giáo Dục.
- 17) Nguyễn Tài Cẩn (1996). Ngữ pháp tiếng Việt (In lần thứ 3), [Vietnamese Grammar, 3th Edition] Hà Nội: Nxb. Đại học Quốc gia.
- 18) Nguyễn Văn Khang (chủ biên), Bùi Chí, Hoàng Văn Hành (2002), Từ điển Mường – Việt [Muong - Vietnamese Dictionary] Hà Nội: Nxb. Văn hóa dân tộc.
- 19) Nguyễn Ngọc San (2003), Tìm hiểu tiếng Việt lịch sử [Exploring the History of the Vietnamese Language]. Hanoi: Nhà xuất bản Đại học Sư phạm.
- 20) Phan, John Duong (2013), Lacquered Words: The Evolution of Vietnamese under Sinitic Influences from the 1st Century bce through the 17th Century ce. Ph.D. Dissertation: Cornell University.
- 21) Pigneau de Behaine, P (1999), Tự vị An Nam –La tinh [Dictionarium Anamitico Latinnum], Hồng Nhuệ Nguyễn Khắc Xuyên dịch và giới thiệu, Nxb. Trẻ.
- 22) Trần Văn Kiệm (1989), Giúp đọc Nôm và Hán Việt [Help reading Nom and Sino-Vietnamese] Nxb. Đà Nẵng-Hội bảo tồn di sản chữ Nôm Hoa Kỳ
- 23) Viện Hàn Lâm khoa học Liên Xô (1987). Tiếng Mường (Язык Мзюнг) [Muong language] Москва.
- 24) Vương Lực 王力 (1948). Hànyǔ Yuèyǔ Yánjiū 汉语越语研究 [Research on Chinese and Vietnamese]. 岭南学报 Línán Xuébào [The Journal of Lingnan College] 9.1:1-96
- 25) Vũ Đức Nghiệu (2011), Lược khảo lịch sử từ vựng tiếng Việt [A brief survey of the history of Vietnamese vocabulary] Hà Nội: Nxb. Giáo dục.
- 26) Vương Lộc (2002), Từ điển từ cổ [Dictionary of ancient words] Nxb. Đà Nẵng-Trung tâm từ điển học.
- 27) <http://www.cema.gov.vn/gioi-thieu/cong-dong-54-dan-toc.htm>